

Whole-genome alignment and recombination detection in the SARS-CoV-2-related clade

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Introduction

Here we describe the parameters used for whole-genome alignment and recombination detection among the complete genomes of the SARS-CoV-2 reference sequence (NCBI's RefSeq accession no. NC_045512.2), a bat-hosted COV RaTG13 (GISAID accession no. EPI_ISL_41402131), a Pan_SL-CoV_GD-like virus (GISAID accession no. EPI_ISL_410721), and two other bat-hosted SARS-like viruses (GenBank accession nos. MG772933.1 and MG772934.1). The main results are also included.

DualBrothers: Recombination Detection Software

Program details and availability

DualBrothers is a recombination detection software based on the dual Multiple Change-Point (MCP) model. This model allows for changes in topology and evolutionary rates across sites in a multiple sequence alignment. We use Bayesian approach together with an MCMC sampling to simulate from the posterior distribution of the dual MCP model parameters. Please, see details of model specification and sampling algorithm in References below.

The DualBrothers plugin written by Prof. Marc Suchard for Geneious Prime® 2020.1.2, Java Version 11.0.6+10 (64 bit), was downloaded from <https://www.geneious.com/plugins/dualbrothers-recombination-detection-plugin/> on July 2, 2020. The program DualBrothers version 1.1 is available at <https://msuchard.faculty.biomath.ucla.edu/DualBrothers/index.html>, accessed on July 2, 2020.

Parameters

- Chain length: 1,100,000
- Subsampling frequency: 10
- Burn-in: 1,000
- Infer changes in: topologies and substitution process
- Preliminary window search
 - Window length: 200
 - Step size: 10
- Model priors:
 - Topology break-points: 0.693
 - Rate change-points: 5
 - Substitution process: estimate hyperpriors

- Window length: 10
- Green's constant: 0.3
- Kappa spread: 0.75
- Mu spread: 0.75

Results

Summary

- Tree 1 (in which SARS-CoV-2 is sister to RaTG13) is preferred in the majority of the positions (210 – 2,177, 2,556 – 22,900, and 23,108 – 29,927; a total of 29,132 nucleotides).
- Tree 2 (in which SARS-CoV-2 is sister to the pangolin-hosted CoV), in which RaTG13 (EPI_ISL402131) is sister to SARS-CoV-2 (NC_045512.2), is preferred from position 1 to 210 (210 nucleotides of the 5'UTR) and from position 22,901 to 23,107 (207 nucleotides of the spike glycoprotein coding gene that includes the ACE2 receptor binding site).
- Tree 3 (in which RaTG13 is sister to the pangolin-hosted CoV), in which RaTG13 is sister to the pangolin-hosted CoV (EPI_ISL410721), is preferred from position 2,178 to 2,555 (378 nucleotides of the nsp2 gene in ORF1a).
- No other trees are highly supported by the data.

The following image shows the alignment of the multiple sequence alignment with 29,927 positions.

Trees

The images below are visual representation of trees 1, 2, and 3, respectively.

TREE 1.

TREE 2.

TREE 3.

Overall alignment visualization

The image below shows the alignment of the multiple sequence alignment with 29,927 positions.

ALIGNMENT OF THE MULTIPLE SEQUENCE ALIGNMENT WITH 29,927 POSITIONS.

Putative recombination at the ACE2 RBM region

The image below focuses on the alignment of the angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor binding motif (RBM) in the spike glycoprotein (S) gene. This is the only region where we found a putative recombination event involving a pangolin-hosted virus influencing the genetic content of SARS-CoV-2.

ALIGNMENT OF THE ANGIOTENSIN-CONVERTING ENZYME 2 (ACE2) RECEPTOR BINDING MOTIF (RBM) IN THE SPIKE GLYCOPROTEIN (S) GENE.

Distances based on identity

	SARS-CoV-2	RaTG13	Pan_SL-CoV_GD	bat-SL-CoVZC45	bat-SL-CoVZXC21
SARS-CoV-2		96.114	90.212	87.683	87.436
RaTG13	96.114		90.143	87.625	87.448
Pan_SL-CoV_GD	90.212	90.143		86.835	86.763
bat-SL-CoVZC45	87.683	87.625	86.835		97.235
bat-SL-CoVZXC21	87.436	87.448	86.763	97.235	

Patristic distances

	SARS-CoV-2	RaTG13	Pan_SL-CoV_GD	bat-SL-CoVZC45	bat-SL-CoVZXC21
SARS-CoV-2		2	3	4	4
RaTG13	2		3	4	4
Pan_SL-CoV_GD	3	3		3	3
bat-SL-CoVZC45	4	4	3		2
bat-SL-CoVZXC21	4	4	3	2	

References

- Suchard, M. A., Weiss, R. E., Dorman, K. S., & Sinsheimer, J. S. (2002). Oh brother, where art thou? A Bayes factor test for recombination with uncertain heritage. *Systematic Biology*, **51**(5), 715-728. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10635150290102384>
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- Minin, V. N., Dorman, K. S., Fang, F., & Suchard, M. A. (2005). Dual multiple change-point model leads to more accurate recombination detection. *Bioinformatics*, **21**(13), 3034-3042. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bti459>

Recombination Inference Program (RIP)

Program details and availability

The Recombination Inference Program (RIP) identifies recombination in a query sequence by calculating its similarity to a background alignment of sequences of different subtypes in a sliding window. Implemented algorithms include similarity and distance plots. A web-based version of RIP version 3.0 is available from <https://www.hiv.lanl.gov/content/sequence/RIP/RIP.html> (accessed on July 1, 2020).

Parameters

The reference sequence of SARS-CoV-2 was used as query. The remaining of the alignment was used as background. Window size was set to 400 nucleotides and the confidence threshold was set to 90%. We strip all gaps and plotted all window values.

Results

Summary

- Significant best match to pangolin-hosted CoV (PAN-SLCoVGD): 417 of 29,903 nucl. (1.39%)
- Total best match to pangolin-hosted CoV (PAN-SLCoVGD): 456 of 29,903 nucl. (1.52%)

- Significant best match to bat-hosted CoV (RaTG13): 26,210 of 29,903 nucl. (87.65%)
- Total best match to pangolin-hosted CoV (RaTG13): 28,658 of 29,903 nucl. (95.84%)
- Other matches: None.

Stats

Significant matches

Terminal	Matches	Significant matches
RaTG13	28,658	26,210
Pan_SL-CoV_GD	456	417
bat-SL-CoVZC45	56	0
bat-SL-CoVZXC21	176	0

Positions identical to the query

Terminal	Positions identical to SARS-CoV-2	Percent. of total positions
RaTG13	28,738	96.03%
Pan_SL-CoV_GD	26,970	90.12%
bat-SL-CoVZC45	26,230	87.65%
bat-SL-CoVZXC21	26,156	87.40%

Identical positions among all terminals

A total of 24,175 nucleotide positions (80.78% of the total alignment) were identical among all sequences (SARS-CoV-2, RaTG13, PanSL-CoVGD, bat-SL-CoVZC45, and bat-SL-CoVZXC21).

References

Siepel, A. C., Halpern, A. L., Macken, C., & Korber, B. T. (1995). A computer program designed to screen rapidly for HIV type 1 intersubtype recombinant sequences. *AIDS Research and Human Retroviruses*, **11(11)**, 1413-1416. <https://doi.org/10.1089/aid.1995.11.1413>